

**Supplemental file to “Analysis of seismically-isolated two-block systems using a multi-rocking-body dynamic model” published in Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering
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Formulation of the post impact velocities for the seismically-isolated two-block system

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1 INTRODUCTION

In this document are presented the post impact velocities for the system of two stacked blocks described in the abovementioned paper. These blocks can rock according to four patterns and the transition between them involves an impact at the base of the lower block or in the middle between the two blocks. The meaning of the terms in the equations is described in the following table. Some of these terms are depicted in Figure 2 of said paper.

mb	Mass of the isolator
kb	Stiffness of the isolator
cb	viscous damping of the isolator
b1	Half thickness of the lower block
b2	Half thickness of the of upper block
h1	Half height of the lower block
h2	Half height of the upper block
m1	Mass of the lower block
m2	Mass of the upper block
h	Height of the center of mass of the combined system (two blocks assumed monolithic)
m	Total mass of the blocks
IG1	Mass moment of inertia of the lower block
IG2	Mass moment of inertia of the upper block
IG	Mass moment of inertia of the combined system (two blocks assumed monolithic)
θ_1	Rotation of the lower block
θ_2	Rotation of the upper block
ub	Horizontal displacement of the isolator
deruBI	Velocity of the isolator before the impact
derthetaBI1	Angular velocity of the lower block before the impact
derthetaBI2	Angular velocity of the upper block before the impact
deruAI	Velocity of the isolator after the impact
derthetaAI1	Angular velocity of the lower block after the impact
derthetaAI2	Angular velocity of the upper block after the impact

2 BASE IMPACTS

From pattern 1a to 2b (or from 1b to 2a)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{deruAI} = & -(((-((IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 \\ & + mb)) + m2^2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (((b1 - b2) * b2 * \text{derthetaBI1} - \text{deruBI} * h2 \\ & + 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * h2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * \text{deruBI} - b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h2 + b2 \\ & * \text{derthetaBI1} * (2 * h1 + h2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) * (m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (IG1 \\ & + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 + ((b1 + b2)^2 + 4 * h1^2) * m2 - (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 + (b1 + b2) * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) - h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 \\ & + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 - (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 + (b1 \\ & + b2) * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) + (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) - m2^2 \\ & * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-b2) * (b1 + b2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + 2 * h1 * h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + 2 * b2 \\ & * h1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + (b1 + b2) * h2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) * ((-m2) * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) \\ & * ((-\text{deruBI}) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + \text{derthetaBI1} \\ & * (IG1 + b2^2 * m2 - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * m2)) + (b1 * b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} \\ & - \text{derthetaBI2}) - \text{deruBI} * h2 - (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2)) * m2 \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * \text{deruBI} + b1 * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * h2 + b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} \\ & + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) - (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * m2 - (b2 * (b1 \\ & + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 + (b1 + b2) * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) \\ & * ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 + mb) - \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (h2 \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) / ((h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) - m2^2 \\ & * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-b2) * (b1 + b2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + 2 * h1 * h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + 2 * b2 \\ & * h1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + (b1 + b2) * h2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) * ((-m2) * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (h1 \\ & * (m1 + 2 * m2) + h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) - (m1 + m2 + mb) * (-IG2 - (b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m2 + (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - (2 * b2 * h1 + (b1 + b2) * h2) \\ & * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) - ((-IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + m2^2 * (h2 \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])^2) * (m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) \\ & * m1 + ((b1 + b2)^2 + 4 * h1^2) * m2 - (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 \\ & * b2 * h1 + (b1 + b2) * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) - h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\ & - (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 + (b1 + b2) * h2) * m2 \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{derthetaAI1} = & (\text{derthetaBI1} * (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) \\ & * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 \\ & * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (-2 * IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) \\ & * mb)) + m2^2 * (((-b2^4) * (m1 + mb) - h2^2 * (IG1 + b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) \\ & + b2^2 * (IG1 + b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 \\ & + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * b2 * (b2^2 * h1 * m1 - h2 * (IG1 - b2^2 * m1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) \\ & * m1) + ((-b1^2) * h2 + (2 * h1 + h2) * (b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2)) * mb) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])) / (m2 * (2 \\ & * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 \\ & * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\ & * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 \\ & + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\ & * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) \\ & * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb)) + m2^2 * ((-2 * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 + mb) \\ & - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) - h2^2 \\ & * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) \\ & + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 \\ & * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b1 * b2^2 * ((h1 + 2 * h2) * m1 + 2 * (h1 + h2) * mb) + b2^3 * ((h1 + h2) \\ & * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) - b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 \\ & * h1 + h2) * mb)) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (\text{derthetaBI2} * (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) \\
& * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 \\
& * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 \\
& * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb))) + m2 * (4 \\
& * b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * ((-b1) * b2^2 * m1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b1 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 \\
& + 2 * mb) + b2 * (h1 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2) * mb \\
& + IG1 * (m1 + m2 + mb))) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (-2 * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 + mb) \\
& - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) - h2^2 \\
& * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) \\
& + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 4 * b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} \\
& * (b2 * h1 * (b2 * m2 + b1 * (m1 + m2)) * (m1 + 2 * mb) - h2 * (IG1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1 \\
& * b2 * m1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h1^2 * (4 * m2 * mb + m1 * (m2 + mb)))) * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + 2 \\
& * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) - b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) \\
& * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) + b2^3 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + h1 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * mb)) + b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h2 * (m1 + mb) + h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (m2 * (2 \\
& * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 \\
& * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 \\
& + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\
& * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) \\
& * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb)) + m2^2 * ((-2 * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 + mb) \\
& - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) - h2^2 \\
& * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) \\
& + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b1 * b2^2 * ((h1 + 2 * h2) * m1 + 2 * (h1 + h2) * mb) + b2^3 * ((h1 + h2) \\
& * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) - b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 \\
& * h1 + h2) * mb)) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 1a to 4a (or from 1b to 4b)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & (-2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) + \text{deruBI} * (2 \\
& * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + m2 * (-2 * (b2 \\
& * (b1 + b2) * \text{deruBI} * m1 - b2 * (b1 + b2) * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{derthetaBI1} \\
& * h2 * (-IG1 + h1^2 * m1 - b2^2 * m2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2)) + b2 * (b1 + b2) * \text{deruBI} * (m2 \\
& + mb) - \text{deruBI} * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b1 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h2 \\
& - (\text{deruBI} - 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1) * h2^2 + b2^2 * (\text{deruBI} - 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (h1 + h2))) \\
& * m2 * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * (b2^3 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m2 - b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * m2) + b2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) - h1 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 + 2 * h2 * m2)) \\
& + b1 * \text{deruBI} * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2 * \text{deruBI} * (h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h1 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * mb))) * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + ((-b2^3) * \text{derthetaBI1} + b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) + b2 \\
& * h2 * (-2 * \text{deruBI} + 4 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 + \text{derthetaBI1} * h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (2 * IG2 \\
& * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + m2 * (-2 * (b1 * b2 \\
& * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b2 \\
& - h2) * (b2 + h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * (b1 * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2 * h2 * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + b2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2] - 2 * b2 * h2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & -(((-(m1 + m2 + mb)) * (\text{deruBI} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) - \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) \\
& * m2) - \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 + b2^2 * m2 - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) + (b1 \\
& * b2 * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) + \text{deruBI} * h2 + (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (b2^2 - 2 \\
& * h1 * h2)) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) * h2 + b2 * (\text{deruBI} \\
& - (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (2 * h1 + h2))) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + h2 \\
& * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) - \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / (m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 \\
& * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
& * (-IG2 - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 + (b2 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - (2 * b2 * h1 \\
& + (b1 + b2) * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 2a to 1b (or from 2b to 1a)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{deruAI} = & -(((-((IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * ((-derthetaBI1) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 \\ & + mb)) - m2^2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((b2 * (b1 + b2) * \text{derthetaBI1} + (\text{deruBI} - 2 \\ & * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1) * h2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * (\text{deruBI} - 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1) + (b1 + b2) \\ & * \text{derthetaBI1} * h2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) * (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (-IG2 - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\ & + ((-b1) * b2 + b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 - b1 * h2 + b2 * h2) * m2 \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 + ((b1 - b2)^2 \\ & + 4 * h1^2) * m2 + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 * h1 \\ & + h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) + (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + m2^2 * (h2 \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (((-b1) * b2 + b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b1) * h2 + b2 \\ & * (2 * h1 + h2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) * (((-derthetaBI1) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 \\ & + mb) - \text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) * (IG2 + (b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m2 + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) \\ & * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (\text{deruBI} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) \\ & - \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) - \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 + b2^2 * m2 - b1^2 * (m1 \\ & + m2) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) + (b1 * b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) + \text{deruBI} * h2 \\ & + (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2)) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * \text{deruBI} + b1 \\ & * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) * h2 + b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2 \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / (((-((IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] \\ & - b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])^2)) * (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (-IG2 - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 + ((-b1) * b2 \\ & + b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (2 * b2 * h1 - b1 * h2 + b2 * h2) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + m2 \\ & * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 + ((b1 - b2)^2 + 4 * h1^2) * m2 \\ & + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2 \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) + (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + m2^2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (((-b1) * b2 + b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) * ((-m2) * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] \\ & - b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + (m1 + m2 + mb) * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 \\ & * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{derthetaAI1} = & (\text{derthetaBI1} * (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) \\ & * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 \\ & * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (-2 * IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) \\ & * mb)) + m2^2 * (((-b2^4) * (m1 + mb) - h2^2 * (IG1 + b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) \\ & + b2^2 * (IG1 + b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 \\ & + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * b2 * ((-b2^2) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1 * h2^2 * (m1 + 2 \\ & * mb) + h2 * (IG1 + b1^2 * mb - b2^2 * (m1 + mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Sin}[2 \\ & * \theta2])) / (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) * (b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 * ((b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * ((b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\ & + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 \\ & + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb)) + m2^2 * ((2 \\ & * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 + mb) - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) - 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 \\ & * (m1 + 2 * mb)) - h2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 \\ & * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 \\ & * \theta2] + 2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b1 * b2^2 * ((h1 + 2 * h2) * m1 + 2 * (h1 \\ & + h2) * mb) - b2^3 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) + b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) \\ & * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (\text{derthetaBI2} * (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) \\
& * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 \\
& * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 \\
& * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb))) + m2 \\
& * (-4 * b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (b1 * b2^2 * m1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + m2) \\
& * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b2 * (h1 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 * m2 + 2 * h2 \\
& * m2) * mb + IG1 * (m1 + m2 + mb))) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (2 * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 \\
& + mb) - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) - 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) \\
& - h2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h2^2 * (m1 \\
& + mb) + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 4 * b1 \\
& * \text{derthetaBI1} * (b2 * h1 * ((-b2) * m2 + b1 * (m1 + m2)) * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h2 * (IG1 * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) + b1 * b2 * m1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h1^2 * (4 * m2 * mb + m1 * (m2 + mb)))) \\
& * \text{Sin}[\theta2] + 2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 \\
& * (h1 + h2) * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) - b2^3 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + h1 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * mb)) + b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h2 * (m1 + mb) + h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb))) * \text{Sin}[2 \\
& * \theta2]) / (m2 * (2 * (b2^2 + h1^2) * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m2 + (b2^2 + h1^2) * (b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m1 * m2) + (b2^2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) + 2 * h1^2 * ((b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * ((b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
& + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 * (m1 + m2) + (2 * m1 + m2) * mb)) + m2^2 * ((2 \\
& * b1 * b2^3 * (m1 + mb) - b2^4 * (m1 + mb) - 2 * b1 * b2 * h2 * (h2 * (m1 + mb) + 2 * h1 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * mb)) - h2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb)) + b2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 \\
& * mb + h2^2 * (m1 + mb) + 4 * h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 * mb))) * \text{Cos}[2 \\
& * \theta2] + 2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2^2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b1 * b2^2 * ((h1 + 2 * h2) * m1 + 2 * (h1 \\
& + h2) * mb) - b2^3 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2) * mb) + b2 * h2 * (IG1 + h1 * (h1 + h2) \\
& * m1 - b1^2 * mb + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 2a to 4b (or from 2b to 4a)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & -((m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (\text{deruBI} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) - \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m2) - \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 + b2^2 * m2 - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1^2 * (m1 + 4 \\
& * m2)) + (b1 * b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) + \text{deruBI} * h2 + (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) \\
& * (b2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2)) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * \text{deruBI} + b1 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) \\
& * h2 + b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) - (IG2 + (b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m2 + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) \\
& * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
& - \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / ((-m2) * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) \\
& * (h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + (m1 + m2 + mb) * (IG2 \\
& + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 + ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b1 * h2 - b2 * (2 \\
& * h1 + h2)) * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * ((b2^2 + h1^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * m2^2 + b2^2 * m2 * mb + h1^2 * (m1 \\
& + 4 * m2) * mb + IG1 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb)) \\
& + \text{derthetaBI2} * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h2^2 * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + b2^2 \\
& * m2 * (2 * m1 + 3 * m2 + 2 * mb)) + m2 * (-2 * (b1 * b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) + (\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * (b2^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * mb))) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - \text{derthetaBI2} * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * (b1 * (\text{derthetaBI1} \\
& - \text{derthetaBI2}) * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
& + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + \text{derthetaBI2} * h1 \\
& * (3 * m1 + 4 * m2 + 2 * mb))) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) / (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h2^2 * m2 * (2 * m1 \\
& + m2 + 2 * mb) + b2^2 * m2 * (2 * m1 + 3 * m2 + 2 * mb) + m2 * (2 * (b1 * b2 * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) - b2^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h1 * h2 * (m1 + 2 * mb)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\
& * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * ((-b1) * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2 * h2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b2 * h1 * (3 \\
& * m1 + 4 * m2 + 2 * mb)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 3a to 1b (or from 3b to 1a)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{deruAI} = & (\text{derthetaBI1} * ((-IG2) * m1 * ((-h1) * IG + h * IG1 + h1 * IG2 + h * h1 * (-h + h1) * m1 + b1^2 * (h \\
 & + h1) * m1) - (IG2 * ((h - h2) * IG1 + 2 * h1 * (-IG + IG2)) + ((-b2^2 + h2^2)) * (h1 * IG \\
 & - h * IG1) + (-2 * b1 * b2 * h + b2^2 * h + b1^2 * (2 * h + 3 * h1 - h2) + h1 * (-3 * h^2 + 5 \\
 & * h * h1 + 3 * h1 * h2 + 2 * h2^2)) * IG2) * m1 + (h * h1 * (-h + h1) + b1^2 * (h + h1)) \\
 & * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1^2) * m2 - (h * h2^2 * IG1 - 2 * h1 * h2^2 * IG1 - h2^3 * IG1 + b1^2 \\
 & * h * IG2 + 2 * b1^2 * h1 * IG2 - 2 * h^2 * h1 * IG2 + 4 * h * h1^2 * IG2 - b1^2 * h2 * IG2 + 4 \\
 & * h1^2 * h2 * IG2 + 2 * h1 * h2^2 * IG2 + h2^2 * (b1^2 * (2 * h - h1 - h2) + h1 * (h + h1 \\
 & + h2) * (-h + 2 * h1 + h2)) * m1 + b2^2 * (-2 * h1 * IG - h2 * IG + h * IG1 + h * IG2 + b1^2 \\
 & * (h + 2 * h1 + h2) * m1 + h * (5 * h1^2 + 4 * h1 * h2 + h2^2 - h * (3 * h1 + h2)) * m1) + b1 \\
 & * b2 * (-2 * h * IG2 + h2 * (IG + IG1 + IG2 + (h^2 + h1^2 - 2 * h * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m1))) \\
 & * m2^2 + (h - 2 * h1 - h2) * (b2 * h + b1 * h2) * ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2^3) \\
 & + \text{deruBI} * ((-h) * h1 * IG2 * m1^2 + h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 - 3 * h * h1 \\
 & * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 5 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 - b2^2 * h * h1 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * h1^2 \\
 & * m1^2 * m2 - h * h1 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 \\
 & - 2 * h * h1 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 - 3 * b2^2 * h * h1 * m1 * m2^2 + 5 * b2^2 \\
 & * h1^2 * m1 * m2^2 - b2^2 * h * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 4 * b2^2 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + b2^2 \\
 & * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 - h * h1 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 - 2 * b2^2 * h \\
 & * h1 * m2^3 + 4 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m2^3 - b2^2 * h * h2 * m2^3 + 4 * b2^2 * h1 * h2 * m2^3 \\
 & + b2^2 * h2^2 * m2^3 + (h1^2 * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 \\
 & + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + IG1 * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) \\
 & * m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b1^2 * (b2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 \\
 & + m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b1 * b2 * m2 * (-2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h2 * m2 * (h * (m1 \\
 & + m2) - 2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * (m1 + m2 + mb)))) / (m2 * (h1 * (h1 - h2) * IG2 * m1 - h1 * h2 \\
 & * (2 * IG2 + h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1) * m2 + b2^2 * ((h1 + h2)^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) \\
 & + (h1^2 * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 \\
 & * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + IG1 * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
 & + b1^2 * (b2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
 & - b1 * b2 * m2 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h2 * m2 * (h2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h1 \\
 & * (3 * m1 + 2 * m2 + 4 * mb))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{derthetaAI1} = & -((\text{derthetaBI1} * (IG2 - b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * (IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + m2 \\
 & * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb + b1 * b2 * (m1 + m2 + mb))) + (-IG2 \\
 & - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (((-deruBI) * h * (m1 + m2) + \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG - (b1 - h) * (b1 \\
 & + h) * (m1 + m2))) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (h2 * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * ((-derthetaBI1) \\
 & * h * (m1 + m2) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2 + mb)))) / ((-IG2 - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * ((-IG1) \\
 & * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b1 * b2 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
 & - h1 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2 * mb + h1 * (m1 + 4 * m2) * mb)) - ((b1 - b2) \\
 & * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + m2 * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 + h2 * (2 * h1 \\
 & + h2) * mb + b1 * b2 * (m1 + m2 + mb))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (\text{deruBI} * ((b1 - b2) * b2 + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 * ((-h2) * m2 + h * (m1 + m2) - h1 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + \text{derthetaBI1} * (b2^2 * IG * m1 * m2 - 2 * h1 * h2 * IG * m1 * m2 \\
& + h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * h2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * h^2 * m1^2 * m2 - b2^2 * h * h1 \\
& * m1^2 * m2 - 2 * h^2 * h1 * h2 * m1^2 * m2 + 2 * h * h1^2 * h2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG \\
& * m2^2 - 2 * h1 * h2 * IG * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h^2 * m1 * m2^2 - 3 * b2^2 * h * h1 * m1 \\
& * m2^2 - b2^2 * h * h2 * m1 * m2^2 - 4 * h^2 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 6 * h * h1^2 * h2 * m1 \\
& * m2^2 + 2 * h1^3 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * h * h1 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 3 * h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 \\
& * m2^2 + h1 * h2^3 * m1 * m2^2 + b2^2 * h^2 * m2^3 - 2 * b2^2 * h * h1 * m2^3 - b2^2 * h \\
& * h2 * m2^3 - 2 * h^2 * h1 * h2 * m2^3 + 4 * h * h1^2 * h2 * m2^3 + 2 * h * h1 * h2^2 * m2^3 \\
& + (2 * h1^3 * h2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 * m2) + b2^2 * m2 * (IG + h^2 * (m1 + m2))) - 2 * h1 * h2 \\
& * m2 * (IG - IG2 - h2^2 * m2 + h^2 * (m1 + m2)) + h1^2 * (IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2) + h2^2 * m2 \\
& * (m1 + 8 * m2))) * mb + IG1 * (IG2 - b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + b1^2 * ((-b2^2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2 * (4 * h1 + h2) * m2 * (m1 \\
& + m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1 * b2 * m2 * (h^2 * m1^2 - h * h1 * m1^2 + 2 * h^2 * m1 * m2 \\
& - 3 * h * h1 * m1 * m2 + h1^2 * m1 * m2 - h * h2 * m1 * m2 + 3 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h2^2 \\
& * m1 * m2 + h^2 * m2^2 - 2 * h * h1 * m2^2 - h * h2 * m2^2 + 2 * h1 * h2 * m2^2 + h2^2 \\
& * m2^2 + (h^2 + h1^2) * m1 * mb + (h^2 + (2 * h1 + h2)^2) * m2 * mb + IG * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)))) / (m2 * (h1 * (h1 - h2) * IG2 * m1 - h1 * h2 * (2 * IG2 + h2 \\
& * (h1 + h2) * m1) * m2 + b2^2 * ((h1 + h2)^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) + (h1^2 * IG2 \\
& * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 * h1 \\
& + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + IG1 * (IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + b1^2 * (b2^2 \\
& * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) - b1 * b2 * m2 \\
& * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + h2 * m2 * (h2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h1 * (3 * m1 + 2 \\
& * m2 + 4 * mb))))))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 3a to 3b (or from 3b to 3a)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & (-2 * b1^2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h * (m1 + m2)^2 + \text{deruBI} * IG * (m1 + m2 + mb) + \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2) \\
& * (h^2 * mb + b1^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb))) / (IG * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (m1 + m2) * (h^2 * mb \\
& + b1^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI1} = & (\text{derthetaBI1} * (IG * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (m1 + m2) * ((-h^2) * mb + b1^2 * (m1 + m2 \\
& + mb)))) / (IG * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (m1 + m2) * (h^2 * mb + b1^2 * (m1 + m2 + mb)))
\end{aligned}$$

3 MIDDLE IMPACTS

From pattern 1a to 2a (or from 1b to 2b)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{deruAI} = & -(((-(\text{derthetaBI2} * \text{IG2} * (\text{IG1} + (\text{b1}^2 + \text{h1}^2) * \text{m1}) + (2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{derthetaBI2} * \text{IG2} + \text{b2}^2 * (2 \\
 & * \text{derthetaBI1} * \text{IG1} - \text{derthetaBI2} * \text{IG1} + \text{derthetaBI2} * \text{IG2} + (2 * \text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) \\
 & * (\text{b1}^2 + \text{h1}^2) * \text{m1}) + \text{derthetaBI2} * ((\text{b1}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * (\text{IG1} + (\text{b1}^2 \\
 & + \text{h1}^2) * \text{m1}))) * \text{m2} + (2 * \text{b2} * \text{h1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h2}) * (2 * \text{b2} * (2 * \text{derthetaBI1} \\
 & - \text{derthetaBI2}) * \text{h1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{derthetaBI2} * \text{h2}) * \text{m2}^2 - \text{deruBI} * \text{m2} * (\text{b2} * (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) \\
 & * \text{h1} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) + \text{h2} * (\text{IG1} + (\text{b1} - \text{h1}) * (\text{b1} + \text{h1}) * \text{m1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2})^2 * \text{m2})) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] \\
 & + \text{deruBI} * \text{m2} * ((-\text{b1}) * \text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} + 2 * \text{b1} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{b2} * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} \\
 & + 2 * \text{h1} * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m2})) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])) * ((\text{b2} * (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h2} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1} * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} \\
 & * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}))) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (\text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} + \text{h2} \\
 & * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m2}) + \text{b1} * (\text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) \\
 & * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) - ((\text{b1}^2 + \text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} + ((\text{b1} + \text{b2})^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m2} + (\text{b1}^2 \\
 & + \text{h1}^2) * (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m} * 1 * \text{m2} + (2 * \text{b2} * \text{h1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h2})^2 * \text{m2}^2 + \text{IG1} * (\text{IG2} \\
 & + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2})) * ((-\text{derthetaBI1} * ((-\text{b1}) * \text{b2} + \text{b2}^2 + 2 * \text{h1} * \text{h2}) * \text{m2} \\
 & + \text{derthetaBI2} * (\text{IG2} + (-\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2}) - \text{deruBI} * \text{h2} * \text{m2} * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + \text{b2} * \text{deruBI} \\
 & * \text{m2} * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])) * (\text{h1} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (\text{b2} * \text{m2} + \text{b1} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) \\
 & - (\text{b2} * (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) - 2 * \text{h1} * \text{h2}) * \text{m2} * ((-\text{deruBI}) * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + \text{mb}) + (\text{derthetaBI2} * \text{h2} \\
 & * \text{m2} + \text{derthetaBI1} * \text{h1} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2})) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (\text{b2} * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) \\
 & * \text{m2} + \text{b1} * \text{derthetaBI1} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])) / (((-\text{m2}) * ((\text{b2} * (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h1} * (\text{m1} + 2 \\
 & * \text{m2}) + \text{h2} * (\text{IG1} + (\text{b1} - \text{h1}) * (\text{b1} + \text{h1}) * \text{m1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2})^2 * \text{m2})) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (\text{b1} * \text{b2}^2 \\
 & * \text{m1} - 2 * \text{b1} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) - \text{b2} * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} + 2 * \text{h1} * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m2})) \\
 & * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * ((\text{b2} * (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h2} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1} * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) \\
 & + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}))) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (\text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} + \text{h2} * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m2}) + \text{b1} \\
 & * (\text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) + (1/2) * \text{m2} \\
 & * ((\text{b1}^2 + \text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} + ((\text{b1} + \text{b2})^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m2} + (\text{b1}^2 + \text{h1}^2) * (\text{b2}^2 \\
 & + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + (2 * \text{b2} * \text{h1} + (\text{b1} + \text{b2}) * \text{h2})^2 * \text{m2}^2 + \text{IG1} * (\text{IG2} + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) \\
 & * \text{m2})) * (\text{b1} * \text{b2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2}^2 * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) - \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (3 * \text{m1} \\
 & + 2 * \text{m2} + 4 * \text{mb}) + (\text{b2}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{b1} * \text{b2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2})) * \text{Cos}[2 \\
 & * \theta 2] + (\text{b2} * \text{h2} * \text{m2} + \text{b1} * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) - \text{b2} * \text{h1} * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2})) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta 2]))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaA1} = & (\text{derthetaB1} * (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 - 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + 6 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} - \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + 5 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 - 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * ((-\text{b2}^2) * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m2}) + \text{h1}^2 * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + 4 \\
& * \text{m2}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + 4 * \text{m2}))) * \text{mb} + 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m2}^2 * (\text{m1} + 4 * \text{mb}) \\
& + \text{b1}^2 * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) \\
& + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + \text{IG1} * (2 * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + \text{mb}) + (\text{b2}^2 \\
& + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2} * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}))) + 2 * \text{b2} * \text{derthetaB2} * \text{m2} * (\text{b1} * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} \\
& + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b1} * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2} * \text{IG2} * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2} * \text{h2} \\
& * \text{m2} * (2 * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + \text{mb}) + \text{h1} * (3 * \text{m1} + 4 * \text{mb}))) + ((-\text{derthetaB1}) * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 \\
& - \text{derthetaB1} * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * (4 * \text{IG2} + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} - (\text{b2}^2 * ((-\text{derthetaB1}) \\
& * \text{IG1} + \text{derthetaB1} * \text{IG2} - 2 * \text{derthetaB2} * \text{IG2} + \text{h1} * (3 * \text{derthetaB1} * \text{h1} + 2 \\
& * \text{derthetaB2} * \text{h2}) * \text{m1}) + \text{derthetaB1} * (4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}))) \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + \text{b1}^2 * \text{derthetaB1} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * ((\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) \\
& + 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{derthetaB1} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{derthetaB2} * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{derthetaB2} * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta] - 2 * (\text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{derthetaB2} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} \\
& + ((-\text{derthetaB1}) * \text{h2} * \text{IG1} + 2 * \text{derthetaB2} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} + \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{derthetaB1} * \text{h1} \\
& + \text{derthetaB2} * \text{h2}) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2}) + \text{b1} * (\text{b2}^2 * \text{derthetaB2} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{derthetaB1} \\
& * \text{h1} * (\text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) + \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{h2}^2 * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{b2}^2 * (\text{m1} + 2 \\
& * \text{m2})))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta]) / (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 + 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + 6 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} \\
& * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2 \\
& * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 5 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 6 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * \text{b2}^2 \\
& * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} + (\text{b2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2) \\
& * \text{IG2} * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2})^2 * \text{m2}^2) * \text{mb} + \text{b1}^2 \\
& * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{IG2} \\
& * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + \text{IG1} * (2 * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + \text{mb}) + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2} \\
& * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{h2} * \text{m2} * ((\text{h1} \\
& + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} + 2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{mb})) + ((-\text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 - \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * (4 * \text{IG2} \\
& + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} - (4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}) - \text{b2}^2 * (\text{IG1} \\
& + \text{IG2} - \text{h1} * (3 * \text{h1} + 2 * \text{h2}) * \text{m1})) * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{h2} * (\text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) + \text{b1}^2 * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * ((\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) \\
& * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta] - 2 * (\text{b1} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 + \text{h1} * \text{m1} * (3 * \text{b1} * \text{IG2} + \text{b2} * \text{IG2} + \text{b1} * (\text{b2}^2 \\
& + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} + (\text{b1} * \text{b2}^2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} + \text{b1} * \text{h1} * (2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}) + \text{b2} \\
& * ((-\text{h2}) * \text{IG1} + 2 * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} + \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1})) * \text{m2}^2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta])
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (2 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m2 * (b1 * h1 * h2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 * mb) + b2 * (h1 * m1 * (h1 * m1 + 5 \\
& * h1 * m2 + 3 * h2 * m2) + 2 * h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2) * mb + b1^2 * m1 \\
& * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG1 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb))) + \text{derthetaBI2} * (h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 \\
& + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 - b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 \\
& * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 - 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m1 \\
& * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (b2^2 * m2 * (IG2 \\
& + h2^2 * m2) + h1^2 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2) - b2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 \\
& * m2))) * mb + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) \\
& + b1^2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) - b2^2 * m1 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) \\
& + IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (b2 - h2) \\
& * (b2 + h2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb))) + (\text{derthetaBI2} * (b1 - h1) * (b1 + h1) * IG2 \\
& * m1^2 + m1 * (2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * (b1 * (b1 + b2) - 2 * h1^2) * IG2 + (b1 - h1) * (b1 + h1) \\
& * (b2^2 * (2 * \text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2^2) * m1) * m2 + (b2^2 * (2 \\
& * \text{derthetaBI1} * IG1 - \text{derthetaBI2} * IG1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * IG2 + (2 * \text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) \\
& * (b1^2 - 3 * h1^2) * m1 - 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * h2 * m1) + 2 * b1 * b2 * (\text{derthetaBI2} * IG2 \\
& + h2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2) * m1) + \text{derthetaBI2} * ((b1^2 - 4 * h1^2) * IG2 \\
& - h2^2 * (IG1 - b1^2 * m1 + h1^2 * m1))) * m2^2) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * (b2 * m2 \\
& * (\text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * IG2 * m1 + ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h2 * IG1 + 2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * IG2 + h1 \\
& * h2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2) * m1) * m2) + b1 * (b2^2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 \\
& * m2 * (h2 * m2 + 2 * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) + \text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 \\
& * m2) + m1 * m2 * (h2^2 * (m1 + m2) - b2^2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (h1^2 * IG2 \\
& * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 \\
& + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 \\
& * m1 * m2^2 + 6 * b2^2 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 \\
& * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (h1^2 * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) \\
& * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + b1^2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 \\
& + 2 * mb) + b2^2 * m1 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) \\
& + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + 2 * b1 \\
& * b2 * m2 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h2 * m2 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 + 2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) \\
& + ((-h1^2) * IG2 * m1^2 - h1^2 * m1 * (4 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 - (4 * h1^2 \\
& * IG2 + h2^2 * (IG1 + h1^2 * m1) - b2^2 * (IG1 + IG2 - h1 * (3 * h1 + 2 * h2) * m1)) * m2^2 \\
& + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2)) + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) \\
& * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * (b1 * h1 * IG2 * m1^2 \\
& + h1 * m1 * (3 * b1 * IG2 + b2 * IG2 + b1 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + (b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h1 \\
& + h2) * m1 + b1 * h1 * (2 * IG2 + h2^2 * m1) + b2 * ((-h2) * IG1 + 2 * h1 * IG2 + h1 * h2 \\
& * (h1 + h2) * m1)) * m2^2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 1a to 3a (or from 1b to 3b)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & -(((m1 + m2) * (h * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-\text{derthetaBI2}) * (IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 \\
& + h2) * m2) - \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 - b1 * b2 * m2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 \\
& * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2))) + \text{deruBI} * (h2 * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 * \text{deruBI} * (m1 \\
& + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + (IG + (b1^2 + h^2) * (m1 + m2)) * ((-\text{deruBI}) * (m1 + m2 + mb) \\
& + (\text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b2 \\
& * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * m2 + b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (m1 + m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / ((IG \\
& + (b1^2 + h^2) * (m1 + m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (m1 + m2)^2 * (h * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 \\
& * \text{Sin}[\theta2])^2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI1} = & (\text{derthetaBI2} * (m1 + m2) * (2 * IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (-h + 4 * h1 + 2 * h2) * m2) \\
& + \text{derthetaBI1} * (m1 + m2) * (2 * IG1 - b1 * b2 * m2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1 * (2 * h1 * m1 \\
& + 8 * h1 * m2 + 4 * h2 * m2 - h * (m1 + 2 * m2)))) + 2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 \\
& + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * mb + 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 - b1 * b2 * m2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) \\
& + h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2)) * mb + 2 * \text{deruBI} * ((-h2) * m2 + h * (m1 \\
& + m2) - h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * (m1 + m2 + mb) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (m1 + m2) * ((b1 * b2 \\
& * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * m2 + b1^2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (m1 + m2) - h * (\text{derthetaBI2} \\
& * h2 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - (b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (h + h1) \\
& * m1 + b2 * (-\text{derthetaBI1} + \text{derthetaBI2}) * h * m2 + b1 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h + 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} \\
& * h1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2) * m2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (2 * IG * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b1^2 + h^2) \\
& * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + (m1 + m2)^2 * ((b1 - h) * (b1 + h) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 \\
& * b1 * h * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 2a to 1a (or from 2b to 1b)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & -(((h1 * IG2 * m1 + h1 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + b2 * ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 \\
& + h2)) * m2^2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b2) * m2 * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + b1 * (b2^2 * m1 \\
& * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-m2) * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 \\
& * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (\text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 + b1 * (b1 + b2) * m2 + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 \\
& + h2) * m2) + \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 - b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) - \text{deruBI} * (h2 \\
& * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] - b1 * \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + (IG2 + b1 * b2 \\
& * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * ((-\text{deruBI}) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (\text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * m2 \\
& + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) * m2 + b1 \\
& * \text{derthetaBI1} * (m1 + m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) - (((h1^2 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 \\
& + IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + b1 * b2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) - h2 * m2 * (IG1 + b1 * ((-b2) * m2 \\
& + b1 * (m1 + m2)))) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b1) * (m1 + m2) * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + b2 \\
& * m2 * (IG1 + IG2 + h1^2 * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-IG2 + (b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m2)) * ((-\text{deruBI}) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (\text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (b2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} - \text{derthetaBI2}) * m2 + b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} \\
& * (m1 + m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * (\text{derthetaBI1} * (b2 * (b1 + b2) \\
& + 2 * h1 * h2) * m2 + \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (-b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) - \text{deruBI} * m2 * (h2 \\
& * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]))) / (((-((h1^2 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 \\
& + 2 * m2) + b1 * b2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) - h2 * m2 * (IG1 + b1 * ((-b2) * m2 + b1 * (m1 \\
& + m2)))) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + ((-b1) * (m1 + m2) * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + b2 * m2 * (IG1 \\
& + IG2 + h1^2 * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2)) \\
& * (m1 + m2 + mb) + m2^2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])^2) + ((h1 * IG2 * m1 + h1 * (2 \\
& * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + b2 * ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2^2) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] \\
& + ((-b2) * m2 * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + b1 * (b2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) \\
& + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) - m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((h2 * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] \\
& + b1 * (m1 + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaA11} = & (\text{derthetaB11} * (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 - 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + 6 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} - \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + 5 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 - 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * ((-\text{b2}^2) * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m2}) + \text{h1}^2 * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + 4 \\
& * \text{m2}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + 4 * \text{m2}))) * \text{mb} - 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m2}^2 * (\text{m1} + 4 * \text{mb}) \\
& + \text{b1}^2 * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) \\
& + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + \text{IG1} * (2 * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + \text{mb}) + (\text{b2}^2 \\
& + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2} * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}))) + 2 * \text{b2} * \text{derthetaB12} * \text{m2} * ((-\text{b1}) * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} \\
& * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + \text{b2} * (\text{IG2} * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{h2} * \text{m2} \\
& * (2 * \text{h2} * (\text{m1} + \text{mb}) + \text{h1} * (3 * \text{m1} + 4 * \text{mb})))) + ((-\text{derthetaB11}) * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 \\
& - \text{derthetaB11} * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * (4 * \text{IG2} + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} - (\text{b2}^2 * ((-\text{derthetaB11}) \\
& * \text{IG1} + \text{derthetaB11} * \text{IG2} - 2 * \text{derthetaB12} * \text{IG2} + \text{h1} * (3 * \text{derthetaB11} * \text{h1} + 2 \\
& * \text{derthetaB12} * \text{h2}) * \text{m1}) + \text{derthetaB11} * (4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}))) \\
& * \text{m2}^2 + \text{b1}^2 * \text{derthetaB11} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * ((\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) \\
& - 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{derthetaB11} * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{derthetaB12} * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{derthetaB12} * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * ((-\text{b2}) * \text{m2} * (\text{derthetaB12} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} \\
& * \text{m1} + ((-\text{derthetaB11}) * \text{h2} * \text{IG1} + 2 * \text{derthetaB12} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} + \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{derthetaB11} * \text{h1} \\
& + \text{derthetaB12} * \text{h2}) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2}) + \text{b1} * (\text{b2}^2 * \text{derthetaB12} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{derthetaB11} \\
& * \text{h1} * (\text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{m2}) + \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{h2}^2 * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) + \text{b2}^2 * (\text{m1} + 2 \\
& * \text{m2})))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 + 2 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + 6 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} \\
& * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}^2 * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2 \\
& * \text{IG2} * \text{m2}^2 + 5 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 6 * \text{b2}^2 * \text{h1} * \text{h2} * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * \text{b2}^2 \\
& * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + \text{h1}^2 * \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2}^2 + 2 * (\text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} * \text{m1} + (\text{b2}^2 + 4 * \text{h1}^2) \\
& * \text{IG2} * \text{m2} + \text{h1}^2 * (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{b2}^2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2})^2 * \text{m2}^2) * \text{mb} + \text{b1}^2 \\
& * (\text{h2}^2 * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{b2}^2 * \text{m1} * \text{m2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{IG2} \\
& * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) + \text{IG1} * (2 * \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + \text{mb}) + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m2} \\
& * (2 * \text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb})) - 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2} + 2 * \text{mb}) + \text{h2} * \text{m2} * ((\text{h1} \\
& + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} + 2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{mb})) + ((-\text{h1}^2) * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 - \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1} * (4 * \text{IG2} \\
& + (\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} - (4 * \text{h1}^2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * (\text{IG1} + \text{h1}^2 * \text{m1}) - \text{b2}^2 * (\text{IG1} \\
& + \text{IG2} - \text{h1} * (3 * \text{h1} + 2 * \text{h2}) * \text{m1})) * \text{m2}^2 - 2 * \text{b1} * \text{b2} * \text{m2} * (\text{h2} * (\text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} \\
& + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2})) + \text{b1}^2 * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}) * ((\text{b2}^2 + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1} * \text{m2} + \text{IG2} * (\text{m1} + \text{m2}))) \\
& * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * (\text{b1} * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} * \text{m1}^2 + \text{h1} * \text{m1} * (3 * \text{b1} * \text{IG2} - \text{b2} * \text{IG2} + \text{b1} * (\text{b2}^2 \\
& + \text{h2}^2) * \text{m1}) * \text{m2} + (\text{b1} * \text{b2}^2 * (2 * \text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1} + \text{b1} * \text{h1} * (2 * \text{IG2} + \text{h2}^2 * \text{m1}) + \text{b2} \\
& * (\text{h2} * \text{IG1} - 2 * \text{h1} * \text{IG2} - \text{h1} * \text{h2} * (\text{h1} + \text{h2}) * \text{m1})) * \text{m2}^2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (2 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m2 * ((-b1) * h1 * h2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 * mb) + b2 * (h1 * m1 * (h1 * m1 \\
& + 5 * h1 * m2 + 3 * h2 * m2) + 2 * h1 * (h1 * m1 + 4 * h1 * m2 + 2 * h2 * m2) * mb + b1^2 \\
& * m1 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG1 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb))) + \text{derthetaBI2} * (h1^2 * IG2 \\
& * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 - b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 \\
& + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 - 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 \\
& * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (b2^2 * m2 \\
& * (IG2 + h2^2 * m2) + h1^2 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 4 * m2) - b2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 \\
& * m2))) * mb - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) \\
& + b1^2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) - b2^2 * m1 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) \\
& + IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (b2 - h2) \\
& * (b2 + h2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb))) + ((-\text{derthetaBI2}) * h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + h1^2 \\
& * m1 * (-4 * \text{derthetaBI2} * IG2 - 2 * b2^2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * (b2 - h2) * (b2 \\
& + h2) * m1) * m2 - (b2^2 * (-2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * IG1 + 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * (3 * h1 + h2) \\
& * m1 + \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG1 - IG2 - 3 * h1^2 * m1)) + \text{derthetaBI2} * (4 * h1^2 * IG2 + h2^2 \\
& * (IG1 + h1^2 * m1))) * m2^2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * (\text{derthetaBI2} * IG2 * m1 + 2 * b2^2 \\
& * \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + (-b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2) - 2 * b1 * b2 \\
& * m2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2^2 * m1 * m2 + \text{derthetaBI2} * IG2 \\
& * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * ((-b2) * m2 * (\text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * IG2 * m1 \\
& + ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) * h2 * IG1 + 2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * IG2 + h1 * h2 * (\text{derthetaBI1} * h1 \\
& + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2) * m1) * m2) + b1 * (b2^2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 * m2 * (h2 * m2 + 2 * h1 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * m2)) + \text{derthetaBI2} * h1 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * m2) + m1 * m2 * (h2^2 \\
& * (m1 + m2) - b2^2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 \\
& * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 \\
& + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 6 * b2^2 * h1 \\
& * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (h1^2 \\
& * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 \\
& * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + b1^2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b2^2 * m1 \\
& * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (IG2 * (m1 \\
& + m2 + 2 * mb) + h2 * m2 * ((h1 + h2) * m1 + 2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) + ((-h1^2) * IG2 \\
& * m1^2 - h1^2 * m1 * (4 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 - (4 * h1^2 * IG2 + h2^2 * (IG1 \\
& + h1^2 * m1) - b2^2 * (IG1 + IG2 - h1 * (3 * h1 + 2 * h2) * m1)) * m2^2 - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 \\
& * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2)) + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 \\
& * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * (b1 * h1 * IG2 * m1^2 + h1 * m1 * (3 * b1 * IG2 \\
& - b2 * IG2 + b1 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + (b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m1 + b1 * h1 * (2 \\
& * IG2 + h2^2 * m1) + b2 * (h2 * IG1 - 2 * h1 * IG2 - h1 * h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1)) * m2^2) \\
& * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 2a to 3a (or from 2b to 3b)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & -(((IG + (b1^2 + h^2) * (m1 + m2)) * ((-\text{deruBI}) * (m1 + mb) + \text{derthetaBI1} * h1 * m1 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] \\
& + b1 * \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) + m1 * (h * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2]) * ((-\text{derthetaBI1}) \\
& * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 + b1 * (b1 + b2) * m2 + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) \\
& - \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 - b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (h2 * m2 + h1 \\
& * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 * \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / ((IG + (b1^2 + h^2) * (m1 \\
& + m2)) * (m1 + mb) - m1 * (m1 + m2) * (h * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + b1 * \text{Sin}[\theta2])^2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI1} = & (\text{derthetaBI1} * m1 * (2 * IG1 + 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) + h1 * (2 * h1 * m1 + 8 \\
& * h1 * m2 + 4 * h2 * m2 - h * (m1 + m2))) + 2 * \text{derthetaBI1} * (IG1 + (b1^2 + h1^2) * m1 \\
& + b1 * (b1 + b2) * m2 + 2 * h1 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * mb + 2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 - b1 * b2 \\
& * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * (m1 + mb) + 2 * \text{deruBI} * ((-h2) * m2 + h * (m1 + m2) \\
& - h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * (m1 + mb) * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + \text{derthetaBI1} * m1 * (m1 + m2) * ((b1^2 - h \\
& * h1) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - b1 * (h + h1) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])) / (2 * IG * (m1 + mb) + (b1^2 + h^2) * (m1 \\
& + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) + m1 * (m1 + m2) * ((b1 - h) * (b1 + h) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] - 2 * b1 * h \\
& * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 4a to 1b (or from 4b to 1a)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{deruAI} = & -(((h1 * IG2 * m1 + h1 * (2 * IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + b2 * ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 \\ & + h2)) * m2^2) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (b2 * m2 * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) - b1 * (b2^2 * m1 * m2 \\ & + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * ((IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 \\ & * h1 + h2) * m2) * ((-deruBI) * (m1 + m2 + mb) + \text{derthetaBI2} * h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + b2 \\ & * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) + m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * ((-derthetaBI2) * (IG2 \\ & - b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) + \text{deruBI} * (h2 * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] - b1 * \text{deruBI} * (m1 + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])) + (1/2) * ((h1^2 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h2^2 \\ & * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) + b1 * b2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) - h2 * m2 * (IG1 + b1 \\ & * ((-b2) * m2 + b1 * (m1 + m2)))) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + ((-b1) * (m1 + m2) * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 \\ & + h2) * m2) + b2 * m2 * (IG1 + IG2 + h1^2 * m1 + (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * (\text{deruBI} \\ & * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + m2 * (\text{deruBI} \\ & * (b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) * m2 * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta 2] - 4 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * (IG2 + h2^2 * m2) \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta 2] + 4 * b2 * h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta 2]) * ((-b2) * \text{derthetaBI2} + \text{deruBI} \\ & * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])))) / (((-((h1^2 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2) \\ & + b1 * b2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) - h2 * m2 * (IG1 + b1 * ((-b2) * m2 + b1 * (m1 + m2)))))) \\ & * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + ((-b2) * (IG1 + IG2 + h1^2 * m1) * m2 - b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2 + b1 * (m1 \\ & + m2) * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2)) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])) * (((-IG2 + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2) * (m1 \\ & + m2 + mb) + (h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] - b2 * m2 * \text{Sin}[\theta 2])^2) + ((h1 * IG2 * m1 + h1 * (2 * IG2 \\ & + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + b2 * ((-b1) * h2 + b2 * (2 * h1 + h2)) * m2^2) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] + (b2 \\ & * m2 * (IG2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) - b1 * (b2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2) + h2^2 \\ & * m2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * ((IG2 + b1 * b2 * m2 + h2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m2) * (m1 + m2 \\ & + mb) - m2 * (h2 * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] - b2 * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]) * ((h2 * m2 + h1 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Cos}[\theta 2] - b1 \\ & * (m1 + m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta 2]))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{derthetaAI1} = & (2 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * ((-b1) * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) \\ & + b2 * (IG2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h2 * m2 * (2 * h2 * (m1 + mb) + h1 * (3 * m1 + 4 \\ & * mb))) - (b1 * IG2 * m1 + (b1 - b2) * IG2 * m2 + h2 * (b2 * h1 + b1 * h2) * m1 * m2) * \text{Cos}[2 \\ & * \theta 2] - ((-b1) * b2 * h2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * h2^2 * m1 * m2 + h1 * IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) * \text{Sin}[2 \\ & * \theta 2])) / (h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + b2^2 \\ & * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 * m2^2 \\ & + 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 6 * b2^2 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 \\ & * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (h1^2 * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) * IG2 * m2 \\ & + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + b1^2 * (h2^2 \\ & * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b2^2 * m1 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 \\ & * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h2 * m2 * ((h1 + h2) \\ & * m1 + 2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) + ((-h1^2) * IG2 * m1^2 - h1^2 * m1 * (4 * IG2 + (b2^2 \\ & + h2^2) * m1) * m2 - (4 * h1^2 * IG2 + h2^2 * (IG1 + h1^2 * m1) - b2^2 * (IG1 + IG2 - h1 \\ & * (3 * h1 + 2 * h2) * m1)) * m2^2 - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 \\ & + m2)) + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta 2] \\ & + 2 * (b1 * h1 * IG2 * m1^2 + h1 * m1 * (3 * b1 * IG2 - b2 * IG2 + b1 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) \\ & * m2 + (b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m1 + b1 * h1 * (2 * IG2 + h2^2 * m1) + b2 * (h2 * IG1 - 2 \\ & * h1 * IG2 - h1 * h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1)) * m2^2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta 2] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (\text{derthetaBI2} * (h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 \\
& - b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 * IG2 \\
& * m2^2 - 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 \\
& * m2^2 + 2 * (b2^2 * m2 * (IG2 + h2^2 * m2) + h1^2 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 4 \\
& * m2) - b2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 4 * m2))) * mb - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + 2 * mb) \\
& + IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + b1^2 * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) - b2^2 * m1 \\
& * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 \\
& + m2 + mb) - (b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + ((-h1^2) * IG2 \\
& * m1^2 + h1^2 * m1 * (-4 * IG2 + (b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) * m1) * m2 - (4 * h1^2 * IG2 + b2^2 \\
& * (IG1 - IG2 - 3 * h1^2 * m1) + h2^2 * (IG1 + h1^2 * m1)) * m2^2 - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2^2 \\
& * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2)) + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * ((-b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 \\
& + m2))) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * h1 * ((-b2) * m2 * (h2^2 * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + 2 * m2)) + b1 \\
& * (IG2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * m2) + m1 * m2 * (h2^2 * (m1 + m2) - b2^2 * (m1 + 2 \\
& * m2)))) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]) / (h1^2 * IG2 * m1^2 + 2 * b2^2 * IG2 * m1 * m2 + 6 * h1^2 * IG2 * m1 \\
& * m2 + b2^2 * h1^2 * m1^2 * m2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1^2 * m2 + b2^2 * IG2 * m2^2 + 4 * h1^2 \\
& * IG2 * m2^2 + 5 * b2^2 * h1^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 6 * b2^2 * h1 * h2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * b2^2 \\
& * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + h1^2 * h2^2 * m1 * m2^2 + 2 * (h1^2 * IG2 * m1 + (b2^2 + 4 * h1^2) \\
& * IG2 * m2 + h1^2 * (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2)^2 * m2^2) * mb + b1^2 \\
& * (h2^2 * m2 * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + 2 * mb) + b2^2 * m1 * m2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + IG2 \\
& * (m1 + m2) * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) + IG1 * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 \\
& * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb)) - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (IG2 * (m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + h2 * m2 * ((h1 \\
& + h2) * m1 + 2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * mb)) + ((-h1^2) * IG2 * m1^2 - h1^2 * m1 * (4 * IG2 \\
& + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m1) * m2 - (4 * h1^2 * IG2 + h2^2 * (IG1 + h1^2 * m1) - b2^2 * (IG1 \\
& + IG2 - h1 * (3 * h1 + 2 * h2) * m1)) * m2^2 - 2 * b1 * b2 * m2 * (h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1 * m2 \\
& + IG2 * (m1 + m2)) + b1^2 * (m1 + m2) * ((b2^2 + h2^2) * m1 * m2 + IG2 * (m1 + m2))) \\
& * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * (b1 * h1 * IG2 * m1^2 + h1 * m1 * (3 * b1 * IG2 - b2 * IG2 + b1 * (b2^2 \\
& + h2^2) * m1) * m2 + (b1 * b2^2 * (2 * h1 + h2) * m1 + b1 * h1 * (2 * IG2 + h2^2 * m1) + b2 \\
& * (h2 * IG1 - 2 * h1 * IG2 - h1 * h2 * (h1 + h2) * m1)) * m2^2) * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2])
\end{aligned}$$

From pattern 4a to 4b (or from 4b to 4a)

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{deruAI} = & \text{deruBI} - (4 * b2 * \text{derthetaBI2} * m2 * (b2 * h2 * m2 * \text{Cos}[\theta2] + (IG2 + h2^2 * m2) * \text{Sin}[\theta2])) / (2 \\
& * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + m2^2 * ((b2 - h2) \\
& * (b2 + h2) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * b2 * h2 * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{derthetaAI2} = & (\text{derthetaBI2} * (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) - (b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 \\
& * mb) - (b2^2 + h2^2) * m2^2 * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2])) / (2 * IG2 * (m1 + m2 + mb) + (b2^2 + h2^2) \\
& * m2 * (2 * m1 + m2 + 2 * mb) + m2^2 * ((b2 - h2) * (b2 + h2) * \text{Cos}[2 * \theta2] + 2 * b2 * h2 \\
& * \text{Sin}[2 * \theta2]))
\end{aligned}$$